

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Exclusive Breast Feeding among Lactating Mothers: A cross-sectional study from KIMS Narketpally, Telangana

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Abstract:

Background: Breastfeeding dramatically decreases neonatal mortality risks if newborns are put to breast immediately after birth. The relationship between early breastfeeding and educational attainment remains inconclusive. Some studies showed higher education levels of mothers positively associated with early initiation of breastfeeding.

Objectives: To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding exclusive breast feeding among lactating mothers.

Methodology: The present cross-sectional study was carried at Department of Paediatrics, Shalini hospital, Hyderabad involving 84 lactating mothers in the post-natal ward. Data was entered into Microsoft excel data sheet and was analyzed using SPSS 22 version software.

Results: In the present study, majority of subjects were in the age group 23 to 27 years (75%). 56% belonged to lower class, 33% to lower middle class and 11% to middle class. Period of lactation was <6 months in 80% and 6 months to 12 months in 20%. Among Positive attitude questions, 85% agreed for continuation of Breastfeeding up to 2 years, 78% agreed for demand breastfeeding, 91% agreed for following vaccination schedule, 87% agreed that health and hygiene are also important for breastfeeding and 81% agreed that breastfeeding increases mother child bonding. 14% took advice from lactation counsellor before breastfeeding, 87% gave breast milk and 13% gave other feeds, 83% were given breastfeeding within 6 hrs, 8% between 6 to 24 hrs and 9% >24 hrs. 84.0% fed on demand, 10% fed at specific intervals and 6% fed at random and 89% never took galactogogues, 9% took weekly and 2% daily.

Conclusion: 96% had knowledge of importance of Exclusive breast feeding. 94% opined exclusive breastfeeding improve immunity. Exclusive breast feeding should be continued for <6 months 16%, 6 months by 78% and >6 months by 6%. 13% gave pre- lacteal feeds to the infant, 87% gave breast milk and 13% gave other feeds, 83% were given breastfeeding within 6 hrs. 89% never took galactogogues, 9% took weekly and 2% daily.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Exclusive Breast Feeding, Lactating Mothers.

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Introduction

Breast feeding is the best essential feeding and breast milk is the best milk. The basic food of infant is mother's milk is the most effective way to provide a baby with a carrying environment and complete food. It meets the nutritional as well as emotional and psychological needs of the infant. [1] Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) is defined as "an infant's consumption of human milk with no supplementation of any type (no water, no juice, no non-human milk, and no foods) except for vitamins, minerals, and medications until six months". EBF for six months

is important for both infant and maternal health. Infants who are not exclusively breast feeding are more likely to develop gastrointestinal infections, not only in developing but also in industrialized countries. The risk of mortality due to Diarrhoea and other infections can increase many-fold in infants who are either partially breastfed or not breastfed at all. During the first two months of life, infants who are not breastfed are nearly six times more likely to die from infectious diseases than infants who are breastfed; between 2 and 3 months, non-breastfed

infants are 4 times more likely to die compared to breastfed infants. [2] Breastfeeding dramatically decreases neonatal mortality risks if newborns are put to breast immediately after birth. The relationship between early breastfeeding and educational attainment remains inconclusive. Some studies showed higher education levels of mothers positively associated with early initiation of breastfeeding. Although parity does not alter early breastfeeding, other studies showed that primiparas mothers, with a lack of previous breastfeeding experience and being of a young age, were more risk factors for delayed initiation of breastfeeding. [3] Exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) is the best nutrition for children for the first six months of life. Exclusive breastfeeding decreases infant mortality due to common childhood illness such as Diarrhoea or pneumonia, and helps for a quicker recovery during illness. Breastfeeding contributes to the health and well-being of mothers; it helps to space children, reduces the risk of ovarian cancer and breast cancer, increases family and national resources, is a secure way of feeding and is safe for the environment. [3-9] By assessing the knowledge, attitude and practices of lactating mothers regarding their child's feeding, an overview can be obtained about the areas which need modifications and hence specific intervention strategies can be made to correct the same. Hence this study was conducted in our institute.

Objectives

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding exclusive breast feeding among lactating mothers.

Materials and methods:

Source of Data: Department of Paediatrics, KIMS, Narketpally, Telangana

Study Population: All Lactating mothers in the post-natal ward of Department of Paediatrics, were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Lactating mother aged >18 years
- Primipara and Multipara mothers

Exclusion Criteria:

- Mothers of Preterm Babies
- Mothers whose neonates were admitted in NICU
- Mothers with breast feeding difficulties such as mastitis, inverted nipples etc
- Mothers who are having psychological illness.
- Mother who had certain disease conditions with contraindications to breastfeeding. e.g. AIDS, Breast cancer.

Duration of study: 8 months

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Sampling technique: Purposive sampling

Sample size: 84

Method of Data Collection:

Information was collected using a structured questionnaire. It was ensured that respondents understand the meaning of questions well by external and internal validation of questionnaire in local language. It included questions on sociodemographic characteristics, child breast-feeding attributes, opinion about colostrum, time of initiating breast feeding and other relevant details. The questionnaire was pilot tested and amended for clarity with the addition of some answer options and was modified accordingly. All interviews and examinations were conducted by single person. Scoring was done for KAP questions. For every correct response score 1 was given and for incorrect response score 0 was given and Total KAP score was calculated.

The Lactating women were given health education by counsellor of the hospital regarding the breast feeding. The lactating women were followed up after 6 months and KAP was assessed among them to determine the effect of health education on KAP of Breast feeding.

Lactating mother's profile: this questionnaire included general profile of the lactating mother where in information pertaining to personal details of the subject such as name, age, address, contact number, occupation, family income, type of family; nuclear or joint, educational status, lactation period and parity was included.

Breastfeeding KAP questionnaire: this questionnaire included close ended questions to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices pertaining to breastfeeding. Items for the knowledge, attitude and practice of EBF scales of the questionnaire were adapted from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) guidelines for assessing nutrition-related knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) manual. This FAO questionnaire has been field tested in several countries to ensure validity, readability, ease of administration and is less burdensome on respondents. Thus, the questionnaire formulated based on the FAO questionnaire was pre tested on 10 women for purpose of precision, validity and easiness of data collection.

Thus, the questionnaire contained 8 questions to assess knowledge. A knowledge score was generated for each mother based on the number of correctly answered questions. These included questions such as, importance of exclusive breastfeeding and colostrums, importance of consumption of galactagogues and knowledge on EBF. The second part of the questionnaire included a 3-point Likert scale to assess the attitude of the lactating mother towards breastfeeding, breastfeeding on demand and importance of breastfeeding over infant formulas. This 3-point

Likert scale provided options such as agree, unsure and disagree. This scale helped in identifying the attitude of the lactating mother capturing the positives and negative attitudes towards breastfeeding. The final part of the questionnaire included a total of 5 questions on breastfeeding practices such as the duration of feeding, providing pre-lacteal feeds, along with nutritional practices such as consumption of traditional galactagogues by the mother for milk production which is highly practiced in South India.

Statistical analysis: Data was entered into Microsoft excel data sheet and was analyzed using

SPSS 22 version software. Categorical data was represented in the form of Frequencies and proportions. Chi-square test was used as test of significance for qualitative data. Continuous data was represented as mean and standard deviation. p value (Probability that the result is true) of <0.05 was considered as statistically significant after assuming all the rules of statistical tests. Statistical software: MS Excel, SPSS version 22 (IBM SPSS Statistics, Somers NY, USA) was used to analyze data.

Results

Table 1: General Profile of Distribution

		Count	%
Age	18 to 22 years	16	16.00%
	23 to 27 years	75	75.00%
	28 to 35 years	9	9.00%
Type of Family	Nuclear	88	88.00%
	Joint	12	12.00%
Education	Illiterate	6	6.00%
	Primary	70	70.00%
	Secondary and above	24	24.00%
Occupation	Homemaker	86	86.00%
	Job	14	14.00%
Socio Economic Status	Lower class	56	56.00%
	Lower Middle class	33	33.00%
	Middle class	11	11.00%
Parity	Primipara	84	84.00%
	Multipara	16	16.00%
Type of Delivery	Normal Vaginal Delivery	88	88.00%
	LSCS	12	12.00%
Number of ANC Visit	1 to 3 times	14	14.00%
	4 to 6 times	86	86.00%
Maternal Lactation Period	<6 months	80	80.00%
	6 months to 12 months	20	20.00%

In the present study, majority of subjects were in the age group 23 to 27 years (75%). 88% of them belonged to nuclear family and 12% belonged to Joint family. 6% were illiterate, 70% studied up to primary school and 24% up to Secondary and higher education. 86% were homemakers, 14% were doing jobs. 56% belonged to lower class, 33% to lower

middle class and 11% to middle class. 84% were primipara and 16% were Multipara. 88% were delivered by Normal vaginal delivery and 12% by LSCS. 14% had 1 to 3 visits during ANC and 86% had 4 to 6 visits during ANC. Period of lactation was <6 months in 80% and 6 months to 12 months in 20%.

Table 2: Knowledge about Breast Feeding

		Count	%
Is exclusive breastfeeding important?	No	4	4.00%
	Yes	96	96.00%
Is colostrum nutritionally beneficial to the child?	No	21	21.00%
	Yes	79	79.00%
Does exclusive breastfeeding improve immunity?	No	6	6.00%
	Yes	94	94.00%
Is it important to initiate breastfeeding within 1 hr. after birth?	No	13	13.00%
	Yes	87	87.00%
Can exclusive breastfeeding prevent child from diarrhoea?	No	26	26.00%
	Yes	74	74.00%
Growth patterns of breastfed infants differ from formula fed?	No	14	14.00%

	Yes	86	86.00%
Consuming galactagogues like almonds and fenugreek can improve the milk production?	No	58	58.00%
	Yes	42	42.00%
How long exclusive breast feeding should be continued?	<6 months	16	16.00%
	6 months	78	78.00%
	>6 months	6	6.00%

In the study 96% had knowledge of importance of Exclusive breast feeding. 79% opined that colostrum was nutritionally beneficial to the child. 94% opined exclusive breastfeeding improve immunity. 74% opined that exclusive breastfeeding prevent child from diarrhoea. 86% of them opined that Growth

patterns of breastfed infants differ from formula fed. 42% opined that galactagogues like almonds and fenugreek can improve the milk production. Exclusive breast feeding should be continued for <6 months 16%, 6 months by 78% and >6 months by 6%.

Table 3: Attitude towards Breast Feeding

Positive Attitude questions	Disagree		Unsure		Agree	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Breastfeeding should be continued up to 2 years?	3	3.00%	12	12.00%	85	85.00%
Do you think breastfeeding should be on demand?	11	11.00%	11	11.00%	78	78.00%
Do you believe in following vaccination schedule?	3	3.00%	6	6.00%	91	91.00%
Do you think health and hygiene are also important for breastfeeding?	12	12.00%	1	1.00%	87	87.00%
Does breastfeeding increases mother child bonding?	10	10.00%	9	9.00%	81	81.00%
Negative Attitude Questions	Agree		Unsure		Disagree	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Do you believe in giving pre-lacteal feeds to babies?	4	4.00%	14	14.00%	82	82.00%
Should breastfeeding be stopped when child has diarrhoeal episodes?	5	5.00%	14	14.00%	81	81.00%
Is formula feeding better than breastfeeding?	8	8.00%	6	6.00%	86	86.00%
Do you believe that breastfeeding causes changes in body shape?	19	19.00%	2	2.00%	79	79.00%

In the study Attitude was scaled in 3-point Likert scale. Questions were divided as Positive attitude related and Negative Attitude Related. Positive questions received 0 score for Disagree, 1 for Unsure and 2 for agreement.

Among Positive attitude questions, 85% agreed for continuation of Breastfeeding up to 2 years, 78% agreed for demand breastfeeding, 91% agreed for following vaccination schedule, 87% agreed that health and hygiene are also important for

breastfeeding and 81% agreed that breastfeeding increases mother child bonding.

Negative questions received 0 score for agreement, 1 for unsure and 2 for disagreement. In the study 82% disagreed for giving pre-lacteal feeds to babies, 81% disagreed for stopping breastfeeding when child has diarrheal episodes, 86% disagreed that formula feed is better than breastfeeding and 79% disagreed that breastfeeding causes changes in body shape.

Table 4: Practices with respect to Breast Feeding

		Count	%
Did you take advice from lactation counsellor before breastfeeding?	Yes	14	14.00%
	No	86	86.00%
Did you give pre-lacteal feeds to the infant?	No	87	87.00%
	Yes	13	13.00%
What was the type of the first feed given to your last child?	Breastmilk	87	87.00%
	Other Feeds	13	13.00%
When did you start breastfeeding after delivering your last child?	Within 6 hrs	83	83.00%
	6 to 24 hrs	8	8.00%
	>24 hrs	9	9.00%
How frequently do you breastfeed?	On Demand	84	84.00%
	At Specific Intervals	10	10.00%

	At Random	6	6.00%
How frequently do you consume galactagogues for improving milk production?	Never	89	89.00%
	Weekly	9	9.00%
	Daily	2	2.00%

In the study 14% took advice from lactation counsellor before breastfeeding, 13% gave pre-lacteal feeds to the infant, 87% gave breast milk and 13% gave other feeds, 83% were given breastfeeding within 6 hrs, 8% between 6 to 24 hrs and 9% >24 hrs. 84.0% fed on demand, 10% fed at Specific Intervals and 6% fed at random and 89% never took galactagogues, 9% took weekly and 2% daily.

Discussion

Global actions towards protecting, encouraging and supporting breast milk as a part of optimal feeding practices among infants has been emphasized since many years however there is incongruence between what is recommended and what is practiced in reality. Therefore, the present study was aimed at identifying the KAP of breastfeeding among lactating mothers. EBF is estimated to prevent approximately one-tenth of child deaths and could play an important role in meeting India's Millennium Development Goal 4 of reducing child mortality. [10] WHO recommends exclusive breastfeeding up to 6 months, in the present study the importance to exclusive breastfeeding was given by 96% of lactating women; however, only 78% were knowledgeable about practicing EBF up to 6 months whereas 16% felt it should be practiced for less than 6 months.

However, a study undertaken in Kerala reports 60% rate of EBF [11] whereas findings from another study are similar which report exclusive breastfeeding for the recommended duration and early initiation of breastfeeding to be poor in Indian scenario. [12] In the present study 85% of lactating mothers felt the need to continue breastfeeding even after 6 months which highlights the unawareness related to initiation of supplementary feeds through weaning at age 6 months. The benefits of breastfeeding were largely accepted by majority of lactating mothers, wherein 94% felt it improved immunity, 79% had knowledge about colostrums being beneficial for the child and 86% agreed on the changes in growth patterns of child fed with breast milk and formula feeds.

In the present study a total of 87% lactating mothers provided breast milk as the first feed for the child. 82% showed a negative attitude towards giving pre-lacteal feeds to their infants yet 13% gave pre-lacteal feeds, this finding is close to the finding reported as 19% use of pre-lacteal feed in one of the studies [7] and a study reported almost double i.e. 32% pre-lacteal feeds given to infants in Kerala [11], Providing the infant with pre-lacteal feeds is a custom practiced in most of the rural and urban sections of India. Pre-lacteal feeds mostly as honey or sugar water happen to be the most common feeds seen in the

present study as well as reported in the study conducted by Mandal et al. 2007. [13] It is believed that pre-lacteal feeds act as laxatives in clearing the meconium.

Sadly, the mothers are not aware that the pre-lacteal feeds that could be a source of contamination. [14] Studies show that the earlier breastfeeding begins the earlier and more effective the consolidation of the process, and therefore, a better impact on the after-birth period, which helps in the earlier initiation of the secretion of breast milk. [15] It was observed that the initiation of breastfeeding within one hour was undertaken by 87% of lactating women which is almost three-fold as compared to the national average of 23.4% (NFHS-3). Knowledge, attitude and practices of breastfeeding differs from Urban to Rural and from Place to place and various factors such as maternal age, maternal education, no of children, socioeconomic status of family, type of family, occupation of mother etc plays a key role in Breastfeeding practices. Hence reinforcement of advantages of breast feeding should be done in Antenatal visits and if health is provided through trained personnel may increase the knowledge on breast feeding.

Conclusion

96% had knowledge of importance of Exclusive breast feeding. 94% opined exclusive breastfeeding improve immunity. Exclusive breast feeding should be continued for <6 months 16%, 6 months by 78% and >6 months by 6%. 13% gave pre-lacteal feeds to the infant, 87% gave breast milk and 13% gave other feeds, 83% were given breastfeeding within 6 hrs. 89% never took galactagogues, 9% took weekly and 2% daily.

Healthcare professionals should go beyond the mere dissemination of information to encouraging and helping mothers to overcome barriers of practicing Breast Feeding and in particular Exclusive Breast Feeding. Informing all pregnant women by Counsellors and other health care providers (ASHA workers/ANM's) at community level about the breastfeeding can be considered as a priority during antenatal visits. Baby Friendly Hospital Initiatives should be undertaken to motivate mothers to breastfeed in postnatal wards.

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